

Deliverable D9.6

Report on Dissemination and Communication activities (2|4)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
RM	Raw Materials
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PCO	Project Coordinator
RP	Reporting Period
SLO	Social License to Operate

1 Executive Summary

This report, titled ‘D9.6: Report on dissemination and communication activities (2|4)’, aims to display all the dissemination and communication activities that DIGIECOQUARRY beneficiaries have been carrying out during the last months.

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium will combine the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates sector, enhance health and safety conditions for workers, improve the selectivity and efficiency of the aggregates sites, maximise sustainability and resource efficiency in quarry operations and foster social acceptance of the extractive industry.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

2 Introduction

Work Package 9: Implementation of the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy seeks to design, execute, monitor and evaluate all the activities related to dissemination and communication carried within the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY. It considers specific actions and establishes the beneficiaries' responsibilities to ensure the project and its results are widely broadcasted and reach the target audience.

On the other hand, this WP also will define a knowledge management strategy according to the background of each partner, the ownership of the foreground identified and the exploitation agreements among the parties.

With the above-stated considered, WP9 outlines (see Figure 2):

- What has been disseminated. Devoting to the basic project-related information delivered throughout the project.
- To whom the project has been disseminated. Consisting of the key stakeholder groups that will be the main audience for the project's public campaign.
- How the project has been disseminated. Including all the channels and tools that will be used by project partners to successfully implement the activities.
- When the project has been disseminated. Providing guidelines to ensure that the timing of the actions is appropriate during the lifespan of the project and beyond.
- Monitoring of the process. Managing the indicators to gauge success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project.

Figure 2. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategy.

2.1 Relation to other activities and deliverables

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies and actions are the cornerstones for generating a deep impact on DEQ's results when attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and social acceptance.

To maximise the impact beyond the project lifetime, these actions will be undertaken within three WPs: WP7. Mechanisms for social acceptance and interaction with policymakers; WP8. Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on RM; and WP9. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation.

These three WPs will closely work during the 48 months the project lasts. Coordination meetings are regularly held to monitor the results achieved within the social, clustering, dissemination, communication and exploitation results.

Figure 3. Relationship between WPs.

2.2 Partners' role in the dissemination strategy

DIGIECOQUARRY partners and their strategic positioning in Europe (and also ASOGRAVAS and MINTEK in Colombia and South Africa, respectively) count with vast capacities to influence the target communities and will act as multipliers. *Table 1* summarises the main dissemination strategies to be implemented:

Table 1. Dissemination Strategy per partner profile.

PARTNERS	DISSEMINATION STRATEGY
Large companies: SANDVIK, METSO, MAXAM, AKKODIS	They have an important influence and impact in the aggregates industry, quarry technology providers, construction and complementary sectors (such as OEMs and 1 st tier providers) including their client networks and commercialisation channels. Dissemination will focus on engaging potential customers interested in exploiting product/services generated.
SMEs: ITK, ARCO, MAESTRO, DH&P, ABAUT, APP, SIGMA, ZABALA	They are mainly interested in attracting new clients and reinforcing the loyalty of customer portfolio thanks to the new competitive advantages acquired related to the KTAs and the IQS. SMEs will make available to DIGIECOQUARRY their existing client/supplier networks as well as the involvement of their Marketing and Communication departments.
Quarries: VICAT, HANSON, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR	They are eager to extend their client portfolio and strengthen links with the already existing ones. Their Dissemination actions will be based on the presentation of improved products (in quality, economic, environmental and social terms) to engage specific stakeholders and end users, mainly in the construction sector (e.g., cement, RMC, road base and subbase, mortar, asphalt, etc). Also, they would like to influence positively the perception of quarrying in the society (see section 2.3).
R&D and Academia: MUL, CHALMERS, UPM, MINTEK, ROCTIM	They aim at engaging with the EU (and also international) scientific and industrial communities to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation and sharing. They pursue the generation of new research lines and training programmes aligned with the key pillars established in H2020. They are seeking to Involve their research groups and communication departments in dissemination activities. Reinforcement of the EU RM' sector.

<p>International cooperation, Promoters & Public bodies: ANEFA, DGASTUR, ASOGRAVAS</p>	<p>They will engage with their network of contacts to maximise their dissemination impact by using their wide partners network, benefiting from their experience/expertise in meetings, workshops and conferences to establish contact and build relations with target groups of the wide range of themes of DIGIECOQUARRY. They would like to bridge the gap between science, practice and society by organising targeted stakeholder workshops to bring together stakeholders, industry, policy makers and citizens to facilitate public acceptance.</p>
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2.3 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled “[D9.6: Report on dissemination and communication activities \(2|4\)](#)”, showcases all D&C activities undertaken between months 12 and 24 of the project to maximise its visibility and impact, with the aim of:

- Effectively promoting the project and its results to all target groups and audiences, both at national and European levels.
- Establishing links and liaisons with international organisations and other interested stakeholders.
- Creating synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives.
- Validating project outcomes to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

2.4 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Report on dissemination and communication activities (2|4)” is structured as follows:

- Section 1 – Executive summary. Contains a brief fact sheet about the project.
- Section 2 – Introduction. Provides meaningful information about WP9, the DCEP and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables.
- Section 3 – Dissemination assets.
- Section 4 – Target groups.
- Section 5 – Dissemination and communication activities.
- Section 6 – Conclusions: Summarises the conclusions of this report as well as the way forward.
- Annexes.

3 Dissemination Assets

DIGIECOQUARRY’s assets and outcomes that are here described, have been disseminated by all partners with a view to maximise the project’s impact and visibility. This information is being conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each stakeholder group, in order to promote not only the project’s results, but also its vision and aim.

- The **conceptual aspects** of the project, meaning the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both on business and at social level, etc.
- The **technical achievements of the project** like the DIGIECOQUARRY IQS platform and the respective ICT infrastructure and needed toolkits. The assets of this category will be highly disseminated on appropriate channel once these tools are developed and thus a more detailed communication strategy will be contained in the next version of the DCEP.
- The **scientific knowledge** that derives from the project in the form of reports, scientific articles, etc.
- All the spectrum of the **project’s activities**, like the four workshops that will be organized in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY, the closing event, the participation in external events and every other action that could be of interest to the project’s target groups.

Figure 4. DIGIECOQUARRY's dissemination assets

4 Target groups

The key stakeholders of DIGIECOQUARRY can be segmented into the four target groups outlined below. The actual stakeholders have been identified and registered in a stakeholders internal Excel worksheet.

- **Business stakeholders:** with potential interest in the project’s successful execution and results that will expand the project’s scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.
- **Academic and research stakeholders:** Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **Governmental and policy stakeholders:** policy makers are of primary interest for the consortium given that they are responsible for setting the guidelines of the current and future mining policies that will affect the commercial feasibility of DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **General public stakeholders:** non-governmental organizations, civil society groups or simply citizens, interested in the potential of DIGIECOQUARRY to address needs relevant to them.

Figure 5. DIGIECOQUARRY’s stakeholders.

Table 2. Target audiences, aims and key messages.

TARGET AUDIENCE	AIM	KEY MESSAGES
Aggregates industries & Quarries / RM Stakeholders and end users Material providers Industry associations and representatives	Final users of DIGIECOQUARRY's result Commercial exploitation Project involvement Clustering via WP8	Main results and experience from pilots Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Economic, investment & cost analysis Prospects of prolonging the productive life cycles of quarries
ICT industry Technology providers Associations and representatives	New range of services in Quarrying the quarry sector Commercial exploitation Open and flexible methodologies for interoperability of ICT tools	Main results and experience reports from the pilots Available materials/services and knowledge generated
Researchers at universities, R&D centres or and Scientific societies in RM	Enhanced scientific knowledge R&D cooperation and promotion Clustering via WP8	Increase data available for research Main results shared in EURMKB and RMIS
Construction sector and other clients	Promote the development of new or improved products and services based on DIGIECOQUARRY results	Improved cost-efficient products, H&S, social & environmental KPIs Raise awareness
Citizens and civil society	General awareness Ensure social awareness of raw materials Project involvement via WP7	Community Engagement Strategies Social Awareness plan Local engagement plan
Policy makers and funding bodies (Government, Regulatory agencies) at local, national and EU level	Provide strong evidence to establish new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for RM Interaction in WP7	Reinforcement of the Quarrying sector Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Raise awareness
Media, journalists and other groups at European level (e.g., environment, energy, safety, NGOs, Consumer's organisations...)	General awareness Improved perception of the extractive industry Trend setters	Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Available materials/services for communication purposes

A preliminary list of identified stakeholders is included in Annex I of *D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan*.

5 Dissemination and Communication activities

5.1 Publications

5.1.1 DEQ website's press releases

DEQ's website frequently releases press clips about the latest updates of the project. They can be found in 'News' section.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/noticias-deq/>

5.1.2 Articles in journals and magazines

Articles about the project have been written in different online and paper magazines. Paper ones can be read in Annex I.

- ANEFA Actualidad by ANEFA:

https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_70_ok

https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_72_web_ab6a66ed2be600

https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_73_web

- Quarry magazine by Maxam:

<https://www.quarrymagazine.com/2022/11/14/maxam-is-focusing-on-customer-solutions/>

- Design and Usage Example of a Data Warehouse in the Context of the DigiEcoQuarry Project by Sigma (paper).
- Stenkoll by Chalmers (paper).
- Cemento y Hormigón by ANEFA (paper).

5.1.3 Scientific publications (journals and congresses)

Several new scientific papers have been published between months 12 and 24 of the project.

- Ortiz, J.E., Torres, T., Sánchez-Palencia, Y., Quílez, L., García, M.J., López-Cilla, I. Geochemical characterization of geological lacustrine formations in Central Spain. (2022) (UPM-AI Team).
 - https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260714_Geochemical_characterization_of_geological_lacustrine_formations_in_Central_Spain
- Ortiz, J.E., Pérez-Fortes A.P., Herrero, M.J., López-Cilla, I., Rodríguez, J.A., Escavy, J.I. La digitalización de minerales y rocas para la enseñanza virtual de Geología (2022) (UPM-AI Team).
 - https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260141_Digitalizacion_de_minerales_y_rocas_para_la_ensenanza_virtual_de_la_Geologia
- Ortiz, J.E., López-Cilla, I., Viladés, L., Luaces, C., Romero, P., Herrero, M.J., Escavy, J.I., Blanco, J.L., Martiarena, L., Eguillor, L., Rico, J., Pérez, C. La enseñanza virtual de geología y minería a través de MOOCS. (2022) (UPM-AI Team).

- <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260294> LA ENSEÑANZA VIRTUAL DE GEOLOGIA Y MINERIA A TRAVES DE MOOCS
- Herrero, M.J., Escavy, J.I, Pérez-Fortes A.P., De la Horra, R., Fregenal, A., Galindo, R., López, F., Menéndez-Pidal, I., Morellón, M., Ortiz, J.E., Sánchez-Moya, Y., Sanz, J., Sanz, E., Trigos, M., Varas, J. Modelos geológicos 3D y digitalización de afloramientos. (2022) (UPM-AI Team).
 - <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260405> MODELOS GEOLOGICOS 3D Y DIGITALIZACION DE AFLORAMIENTOS
- Bernardini, M., Paredes, C., Sanchidrián, J.A., Segarra, P., Gómez, S. On the Influence of Sampling Scale on the In Situ Block Size Distribution. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*: 55, 5723–5738. (2022). (UPM-M Team).
 - <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-02953-1>
- Gómez, S., Sanchidrián, J.A., Segarra, P., Bernardini, M. A Non-parametric Discrete Fracture Network Model. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*: 56, 3255–3278 (2023). (UPM-M Team).
 - <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-03194-y>
- Coronel-Gavira, J., Yagüe-Jiménez, V., Blanco-Murillo, J.L. Radiofrequency absorbance as a novel concentration indicator in sucrose aqueous solutions. *Ingeniería e Investigación*: 43(1), (2022). (UPM-AI Team).
 - DOI: [10.15446/ing.investig.94695](https://doi.org/10.15446/ing.investig.94695)
- Cámara Largo, M.J., Blanco-Murillo, J.L. Acercando los autocodificadores variacionales al gran público. TECNIACÚSTICA 2022 (53^º International conference of acoustic technologies). Awarded Andres Lara special mention to the best publication presented by a young researcher. Permanent. (UPM-AI Team).
 - <https://documentacion.sea-acustica.es/publicaciones/Elche22/ID-55.pdf>

5.1.4 Public deliverables

Several deliverables have been submitted to the European Commission for their assessment. The ones that can be shared with the general public are uploaded on the project website:

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/deliverables/>

5.2 Participation in events, trade fairs and workshops

Between months 12 and 24, DIGIECOQUARRY's consortium partners have participated in several external events to show their activities and results.

Besides, a list of identified events, fairs and workshops can be found in *D9.1 Annex XII*.

5.2.1 SBMI Production I

Chalmers University organised in November 2022 a workshop with Swedish aggregate producers on process modelling and how to incorporate environmental impact in process evaluation.

Figure 6. SBMI programme.

5.2.2 X USATIC International Congress

In June 2022, UPM-AI presented an oral communication in the USATIC 2022 International Congress, named: La digitalización de minerales y rocas para la enseñanza virtual de Geología (Ortiz, J.E., Pérez, P., Herrero, M.J., López Cilla, I., Peña, C., Rodríguez-Rama, J.A., Escavy, J.I.).

5.2.3 IMPC Asia-Pacific 2022 (Conference)

In this industry conference in August 2022, an oral presentation on environmental impacts from assets in aggregates production and DEQ's work continuity were discussed by Chalmers University.

Figure 7. DEQ at IMPC Asia Pacific,

5.2.4 Sexto Encuentro Nacional de la Industria de Agregados

Hosted by Asogravas, it was held during the 7th, 8th, and 9th of September 2022.

Figure 8. Pictures taken during Sexto Encuentro Nacional de la Industria de Agregados in Colombia.

5.2.5 Radio interview for a national radio station (in Spanish)

Paulo Romero, from ANEFA, participated in a radio programme in which he talked about the improvements that DEQ will bring to the aggregates sector.

<https://javier-pascual.com/la-industria-de-los-aridos-en-espana/>

5.2.6 Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry - SDIMI 2022

Montanuniversität Leoben participated in SDIMI 2022, an international conference that gathered government representatives, industry experts, academia, NGOs, and civil society. An oral presentation and the publication of an extended abstract on energy efficiency in the aggregate sector, and the description of DEQ's approach on this matter and next steps were provided.

<https://sdimi.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/SDIMI-2022-Final-Programme-12092022.pdf>

The submitted abstract can be read in Annex II.

5.2.7 FECIES 2022

UPM-AI organised a Symposium named "Digitalization and TICs for Teaching and Research in Earth Sciences and Mining" within the International Congress on Evaluation of the Quality of Research and Higher Education (FECIES) (28th-30th September 2022). In this Symposium, UPM-AI presented some advances in digitalisation to obtain 3D models and innovative ways to spread knowledge about mining and geology. They also presented two oral communications:

Virtual teaching of Geology and Mining through MOOCs (Ortiz, J.E., López Cilla, I., Viladés, L., Luaces, C., Romero, P., Herrero, M.J., Escavy, J.I., Blanco, J.L., Martiarena, L., Eguillor, L., Rico, J., Gavilanes, J., Pérez, C., Sánchez-Palencia, Y.). 3D Geological models and digitalization of outcrops (Herrero., Escavy, J.I., Pérez-Fortes, A.P., Ortiz, J.E., et al.).

<https://www.forofecies.com/copy-of-programa-1>

5.2.8 Jornadas de otoño - Emprendimiento e innovación hacia la sostenibilidad

ETSI Minas held an innovation and technology transfer forum focused on women, science and industry. Its aim was to promote the creation of scientific-technological networks between women in the energy, environment, circular economy, energy transition and mobility sectors.

ANEFA presented the project, its goals and achievements.

Figure 9. DEQ at Emprendimiento e innovación hacia la sostenibilidad fórum.

5.2.9 Fragblast 13

UPM-M participated in the 13th International Symposium on rock fragmentation by blasting (17th – 19th October 2022). The reference of this work is:

P. Segarra, M. Laguillo, J. A. Sanchidrián, F. Beitia, Mechanically operated probe to survey ring-blastholes in a safe and efficient way, Proc. 13th International Symposium on Rock Fragmentation by Blasting, Hangzhou, China, 17-19 octubre 2022. China Society of Explosives and Blasting, pp. 763-774.

The submitted article which features DEQ can be found in Annex II.

5.2.10 Bauma 2022

Bauma 2022, held between the 24th – 30th October 2022 was the hub of the mining industry. Exhibitors in the mining sector showed the latest practical trends and provided insights into current topics in the mining industry. ITK presented the DEQ project in the Mining Hall.

Figure 10. DEQ at BAUMA.

5.2.11 Swedish Mining Innovation PhD Student network workshop

In November 2022, Chalmers University participated in a workshop with Swedish PhDs and industry companies involved in mining. An oral presentation on research within DEQ was done.

The programme can be found in Annex II.

5.2.12 MaPric

On the 9th of November 2022, Asogravas disseminated DEQ at MaPric’s event. MaPric is a project to develop strategies to increase resource efficiency and reduce Greenhouse Gases Emissions in South America.

Figure 11. DEQ at MaPric.

5.2.13 Spanish Science Week

The Spanish Directorate General for Cultural Heritage celebrated the Science and Innovation Week by organising activities offering a scientific-technical look at cultural heritage between the 7th and the 20th of November 2022, free of charge to the general public. The project was promoted and presented by UPM-AI.

Figure 12. Poster used during Science week to disseminate DEQs activities.

5.2.14 BIMExpo

A joint team from ANEFA and APP presented in November 2022 the project in BIMExpo. It is a technical congress with exhibition with the aim of accelerating the implementation of BIM and its use in the domestic and international market, promoting and developing open standards for the exchange of information related to buildings and infrastructures, and serving as a platform to boost the knowledge and professionalization of BIM in the construction industry.

Figure 13. APP and ANEFA at BIMExpo

5.2.15 Raw Materials week

UPM-AI took part in the Raw Materials Week (November 14-18th 2022), specifically the attending the online 9th Annual High-Level Conference of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on raw materials, including EU-Ukraine strategic partnership on raw materials and batteries.

https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/events/raw-materials-week-2022-2022-11-14_en

5.2.16 ANEPLA assembly

Celebrated in Bergamo, Italy, it took place on the 25th of November 2022. ANEPLA is the Italian aggregates association, of which Holcim Italy is an active member. Paolo Zambianchi, leader of the pilot sites of the Project, presented DEQ.

<http://www.anepla.it/assemblea-ordinaria-anepla-2022-e-rinnovo-presidenza/>

5.2.17 ForumMiro

DHP presented their work within the project during ForumMiro.

Figure 14. DHP team during Forum Miro.

5.2.18 Seminar for Advancement of the Aggregate Industry

The Project Coordinator, César Luaces Frades, introduced DEQ at the Seminar for Advancement of the Aggregates Industry held in Seoul, South Korea, in November 2022.

Figure 15. DEQ in Korea.

5.2.19 ISEE

DEQ was present at the highly influential International Society of Explosives Engineers' Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting Techniques thanks to UPM-M in February. Santiago Gómez (UPM-M Team) presented in this conference the paper:

Gómez S, Sanchidrián JA, Segarra P. 2023. Shock Impedance Method Applied to Detonation Pressure Measurements. 49th Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting Technique. San Antonio, TX, USA, 6-7 February 2023. International Society of Explosives Engineers.

Figure 16. DEQ at ISEE.

5.2.20 AFA Extremadura and Castilla La Mancha meetings

DEQ developments are always presented when ANEFA organises meetings with their associated companies and members.

Figure 17. DEQ in ANEFA's meetings.

5.2.21 Workshop Holcim

On March 8th, Holcim Italy organised a workshop in which the project and its developments were discussed.

Figure 18. Holcim's workshop including DEQ

5.2.22 PDAC

Lorena Viladés, ANEFA's coordination team member, was part of the important delegation the European Commission sent to PDAC 2023, the world's premier mineral exploration & mining convention that took place in Toronto on March, from the 5th to the 8th.

Figure 19. DEQ at PDAC.

5.2.23 AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries

Sigma and ANEFA held a joint Webinar about the use of Artificial Intelligence for aggregate quarries on the 15th of March.

Figure 20. AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries.

5.2.24 Visit to aggregate quarries with University students

The DIGIECOQUARRY Project organised a field trip (11th - 12th March, 2023) with university students to aggregate quarries in which its main objectives were discussed.

Figure 21. Field trip organized by DIGIECOQUARRY to a quarry in northern Spain.

5.2.25 Hannover Messe

On the 18th of April, during the EU Research & Innovation for sustainable and efficient raw materials value chains, six raw materials projects managed by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) presented their successful results at Hannover Messe, one of the world’s largest industrial trade fairs.

Acting on behalf of ANEFA, was Lorena Viladés Santos, one of the coordinators. Viladés introduced the project and described the main goals, the structure, and the advances of the project so far.

Figure 22. DEQ at Hannover Messe

5.2.26 Expomin

Asogravas has widely disseminated DEQ at Expomin (24th – 27th April, Chile), the largest mining fair in Latin America. This is consolidated as a space that promotes the transfer of knowledge, experiences and especially the offer of technologies that contribute to innovation and increase the productivity of mining processes.

Figure 23. DEQ at Expomin 2023.

5.2.27 Energy efficiency workshop

On the 3rd of May 2023, ANEFA organised a workshop about energy efficiency in aggregates sites with more than 40 attendees. ANEFA and MAXAM talked about their role and explained their developments within the project.

Figure 24. DEQ by ANEFA and MAXAM at a workshop.

5.2.28 SaMoTer – Veronafiere

SaMoTer took place from 3rd to 7th of May 2023, in Verona. It is the only event in Italy to embrace all sectors of construction machinery, and DEQ was present thanks to Ma-Estro at their booth.

Figure 25. DEQ at SaMoTer.

They also organised a joint workshop with Holcim Italy, in which they talked about DEQ.

Figure 26. Joint workshop Ma-Estro and Holcim.

5.2.29 ANEFA's general Assembly

DEQ's current status was explained to all ANEFA's member during its general assembly.

Figure 27. DEQ at ANEFA's general assembly.

5.2.30 Andesit „Gestein des Jahres 2020/21“

With an impressive event at the Mammendorf quarry in the Flechting mountain range, which belongs to the Pescher Group (Cronenberger Steinindustrie), andesite was honoured as the "Rock of the Year 2020/21". DEQ was presented during the opening speech.

Figure 28. DEQ in Andesit „Gestein des Jahres 2020/21“

5.3 DIGIECOQUARRY's workshops, seminars & panel presentations

A list of identified workshops, seminars & panel presentations can be found in D9.1 Annex XIV.

5.3.1 MOOC

The first edition of “Los áridos” MOOC, developed by UPM-AI, Sigma, ANEFA and ZABALA, started on the 16th of May 2023 and will end on the 10th of July. It is free of charge and for following it and passing the tests of each module a certificate is obtained.

<https://miriadax.net/curso/los-aridos-mineria-aplicacion-digitalizacion-y-sostenibilidad/>

The screenshot shows the MIRIADAX website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "¿Qué quieres estudiar?" and a dropdown menu for "Todas las categorías". Below the search bar, there are navigation links for "APRENDE" and "MIRIADAX EMPRESAS", and a "Volver a Inicio" button. The main content area displays the MOOC "Los áridos: minería, aplicación, digitalización y sostenibilidad" with a price of "0,00€". The course description states: "MOOC dirigido a conocer el origen y los procesos de extracción, tratamiento y procesamiento de los áridos, que son las materias primas más usadas después del agua, así como conocer su aplicación en la vida diaria y en la industria. Incluyendo los aspectos relacionados con la sostenibilidad, medio ambiente y dimensión social, junto con la digitalización e inteligencia artificial de los procesos." The course is taught by the "UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID" in the "CIENCIAS E INGENIERÍA" category.

Figure 29. MOOC “Los áridos: minería, aplicación, digitalización y sostenibilidad”

5.4 On-line presence

5.4.1 Project's social media accounts & network with partner's social media profiles

Nowadays, social media profiles are considered key for the communication of the project. Since their creation, WP9 has been updating them by keeping up with DEQ's latest news and facts about the project.

DIGIECOQUARRY's social media URLs are:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Digiecoquarry>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiecoquarry/>
- Instagram: @digiecoquarry
- Twitter: @digi_eco

- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>
- Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/digiecoquarry>

Direct access to DIGIECOQUARRY's social media is available on the website.

ANEFA administrates DIGIECOQUARRY's social media accounts, but all partners are required to actively interact with them, as well as to publish posts and news about DIGIECOQUARRY regularly through the social media of their organizations.

Partners' social media list is shown in *D9.1. Annex XVI*.

5.4.2 Videos

New videos have been uploaded to DEQ's YouTube channel and Vimeo. They are explained in *D9.6 Dissemination and communication materials (2|4)*.

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>

5.4.3 Research Gate

An account in Research Gate has been created to share the scientific publications derived from the project.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Digiecoquarry-Project>

Research Gate aims to connect the world of science and make research open to all. Twenty million researchers coming from diverse sectors in over 190 countries use this platform to connect, collaborate, and share their work.

Figure 30. DEQ's Research Gate profile.

5.5 Other channels & tools

5.5.1 Partners' communication channels

DIGIECOQUARRY taps the support of partners' communication channels. During these months they have been publishing about the project in their social media, webpages, and intranets. Links to partners' publications are collected.

- Federación de áridos by ANEFA

<https://aridos.info/otras-actividades-han-completado-el-programa-del-vi-congreso-nacional-de-aridos/>

- ANEFA Online 185. June 2022

<https://www.aridos.org/proyectos-europeos-firma-de-un-grant-agreement-inteligencia-artificial-broche-de-oro-y-un-premio/>

- ANEFA Online 188. October 2022

<https://www.aridos.org/cuenta-atras-para-milan/>

- ANEFA Online 189. November 2022

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-celebra-su-reunion-anual-en-milan/>

- ANEFA Online 190. December 2022

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-cierra-el-ano/>

- ANEFA Online 191. January 2023

<https://www.aridos.org/la-primera-version-de-los-data-lake-del-proyecto-deq-inicia-sus-pruebas-en-los-5-pilotos/>

- ANEFA Online 192. February 2023

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-en-valdilecha-nuevo-video/>

- ANEFA Online 193. March 2023

<https://www.aridos.org/anefa-en-el-evento-minero-mas-importante-del-mundo-liderando-deq-rotate/>

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-aprueba-con-nota-la-primera-revision-tecnica-de-la-comision-europea/>

- ANEPLA by Holcim

<http://www.anepla.it/digiecoquarry-meeting-a-milano/>

The list of Partners' communication channels is shown in D9.1 Annex XIX.

5.5.2 Synergies with relevant projects and initiatives

Between months 12 and 24, DIGIECOQUARRY has held some clustering meetings with other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects as:

ROTATE: <http://rotateproject.eu/>

IlluMINEation: <https://www.illumineation-h2020.eu/>

Briefcase: <http://briefcase.eitrawmaterials.eu/the-project>

Dig_IT: <https://digit-h2020.eu/>

ICEBERG: <https://iceberg-project.eu/>

RAWMINA: <https://rawmina.eu/>

ROBOMINERS: <https://robominers.eu/>

SUMEX: <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

Sea4value: <https://sea4value.eu/>

5.5.3 Meetings with policy makers (at EU and national levels)

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) closely collaborate and coordinate the organisation of meetings with policy makers at EU and national level to explain DIGIECOQUARRY. This aims to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation or other).

6 KPIs

An evaluation of the KPIs for the implementation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan can be seen below.

As shown, some of the KPIs have not even started yet. This is due to the fact that, for some of them, the project needs further development, meaning the start of the field tests. It would be pointless to launch further scientific publications and technical conferences without any tangible results, or trainings sessions on a tool which is still being developed.

However, on the other hand, the Consortium has been very active participating in events, fairs, and publishing articles about the day-to-day of the project. So far, the Consortium has already achieved several KPIs.

Annex III contains a track record of all the activities carried out by each beneficiary.

Table 3. D&C KPIs

	KPI	(A)	(B)	(B/A%)	(B/A/48*Month of the project)-1
		Final Target (GA)	Actions achieved as today	% of implementation	% Relative deviation
FOR ALL	Participation in scientific conferences.	48	13	27.1%	-45.8%
	Participation in events/fairs/workshops.	25	37	148.0%	196.0%
	Scientific publications.	26	9	32.7%	-34.6%
	Publications in paper magazines, websites and social media.	32	36	112.5%	125.0%
FORUMS ORGANISED BY ANEFA	Open-door symposia.	10	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Joint co-creation meetings.	2	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Global Innovation and Technology Conference in the RM sector.	1	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	New sector and Expert Forum.	1	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Presentations in different Committee Meetings.	8	4	50.0%	0.0%
	Presentations in the Entrepreneurs Forum.	2	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Seminars and panel discussion and networking meeting in the Spanish National Aggregates Congress 2022 & 2025.	2	1	50.0%	0.0%
	Workshop in the ANEFA Chair in Aggregate Technology.	1	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Workshop in the European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining.	1	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Project workshops.	4	1	25.0%	-50.0%
SOCIAL	Meetings with neighbourhood or community reference group.	10	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Enquiries from citizens received.	40	0	0.0%	-100.0%
POLICY MAKERS	Policy makers: meetings at European level.	10	4	40.0%	-20.0%
	Policy makers: 20 meetings at national level.	20	7	35.0%	-30.0%
	Clustering events	30	18	60.0%	20.0%
EXPLOITATION PLAN	Guidance roadmaps for the extractive industry.	3	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Capacity Building Program.	1	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Training sessions.	3	0	0.0%	-100.0%
ONLINE PRESENCE	Logo.	1	1	100.0%	100.0%
	Project website.	1	1	100.0%	100.0%
	Visits in the project website.	70000	767	1.1%	-97.8%
	Website updates in the project period.	6	3	50.0%	0.0%
	Followers in social media.	1000	857	85.7%	71.4%
	Communication materials/year.	24	11	45.8%	-8.3%
	Press release, article, interview	64	28	43.8%	-12.5%
	Newsletters.	6	0	0.0%	-100.0%
	Videos.	2	12	600.0%	1100.0%

7 Conclusions

This document, titled “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (2|4)”, describes the articles, activities and all dissemination items related to DEQ that have been undertaken between months 12 and 24 of the project. This document will be updated in months 36 and 48.

8 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.

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11Annex I. Paper articles

Cemento y Hormigón by ANEFA

CyA

CANTERAS y ÁRIDOS

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DigiEcoQuarry, el presente de las canteras del futuro

DigiEcoQuarry es un proyecto tecnológico que va a ser fundamental para la minería del futuro y del presente. Es una aventura investigadora que nace de la intersección entre inteligencia artificial, digitalización y sostenibilidad y se proyecta hacia el desarrollo sostenible. Hoy, gran parte de las canteras se están quedando atrás en el aprovechamiento de las enormes ventajas económicas y sociales que aporta lo que se ha dado en llamar la 'minería 4.0'. Esta iniciativa aspira a cambiar esta dinámica y a liderar el gran cambio que se avecina.

Cuatro años. Ese es el tiempo que tiene DigiEcoQuarry para revolucionar la manera en la que concebimos el trabajo en una cantera. Este proyecto, financiado con 13 millones de euros dentro del programa 'Horizonte 2020' de la Comisión Europea, incide en la importancia vital de un sector industrial, el de las materias primas, que es considerado estratégico por la Unión Europea (UE), más aún en las actuales circunstancias geopolíticas. Esta iniciativa, de hecho, se pone en marcha para ejercer de palanca en la aspiración de solucionar la dependencia actual de la UE en lo relativo a las materias primas minerales. La estrategia a largo plazo es fijar las cadenas de valor industriales en suelo europeo, desde la extracción al procesamiento industrial final, colaborando en la reducción de las emisiones de CO₂; asegurando la independencia y la capacidad de producción europea. Es un cambio de paradigma: es necesario disponer de un sector extractivo de vanguardia, respetuoso con el entorno, eficaz y competitivo.

El proyecto nace para responder a este enorme desafío: conectar todos los procesos que tienen lugar en una explotación minera e integrar toda su coordinación y funcionamiento en tiempo real para mejorar y optimizar sus operaciones. Esto implica unos considerables beneficios en cuanto a eficacia, eficiencia, consumo, etc. El equipo que forma este ambicioso proyecto, en el que participan instituciones de 10 países, es impulsar todo el potencial que pueden tener las canteras digitales a través de avances en los procesos de digitalización y automatización. Debemos recordar, en este sentido, que la política industrial europea considera a las materias primas como una de las seis áreas estratégicas de la UE, ya que son vitales para la consecución de la autonomía estratégica, los objetivos de neutralidad climática y la transición energética.

Lo que persigue DigiEcoQuarry es desarrollar sistemas, tecnologías y procesos para impulsar la digitalización y la automatización de las canteras de forma que

Logotipo DigiEcoQuarry.

sean más seguras, sostenibles y eficientes. Para lograrlo, se combinan enfoques de inteligencia artificial (o también 'IA', como herramientas de gestión de acopios y de diagnóstico remoto de equipos), sistemas ciber físicos (por ejemplo, monitorizar la producción) y el internet de las cosas (o 'IoT', como el control de parámetros medioambientales de forma remota y automática).

Digitalización y 'minería 4.0'

El proyecto DigiEcoQuarry, centrado en el sector de los áridos, busca digitalizar tanto canteras como graveras mediante el desarrollo de una plataforma de gestión global que permita controlar, en tiempo prácticamente real, los procesos que se llevan a cabo en una explotación. Esta plataforma, bautizada como Innovative Quarrying System (IQS), es el corazón de este proyecto. Esta herramienta consistirá en diferentes módulos en los que se podrán visualizar aspectos como el estado de las voladuras, el consumo de la flota móvil y el rendimiento de la planta. Asimismo, se podrán también monitorizar, mediante un simulador ambiental, las emisiones a la atmósfera producidas por la actividad de la explotación.

Dentro del marco del proyecto también se incluyen la realización de actividades con comunidades aledañas para mejorar la percepción del sector y acciones conjuntas con otros proyectos financiados por la Comisión Europea para intercambiar experiencias y conocimiento.

Para lograr esta meta, el consorcio que forma DigiEcoQuarry está integrado por un equipo multidisciplinar de veinticinco organizaciones de ocho países europeos y otros dos de otros continentes (Colombia y Sudáfrica), entre los que se encuentran asociaciones empresariales, como ASOGRAVAS o ANEFA, que, además lidera el proyecto; multinacionales del sector (Sandvik, Metso: Outotec, Maxam); universidades y centros tecnológicos (Montanuniversität Leoben, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola, Mintek) o empresas (AKKODIS High Tech; Arco Electrónica; Ma-estro; Dohmen, Herzog & Partner; Abaut; APP Consultoría de Gestión de Proyectos; Sigma Technologies; ITK Engineering GmbH; Roctim; Zabala Innovation Consulting) y cinco pilotos donde se prueban los avances tecnológicos del equipo: Granulats VICAT (Francia); Cronenberger Steinindustrie Franz Triches (Alemania); Agrepor Agregados (Portugal); Holcim Italia y Hanson Hispania. A ellos se suma la Dirección General de Minería y Energía del Principado de Asturias.

Validación de resultados

En el ADN de este proyecto está su aplicación directa a las canteras. DigiEcoQuarry trabaja desde, en y para las canteras y graveras. Por ello las soluciones tecnológicas que se desarrollen durante nuestras investigaciones se validarán en cinco proyectos piloto. Estos cinco emplazamientos han sido seleccionados especialmente para representar la enorme variedad de necesidades de las 26.000 explotaciones de áridos de la UE. Nuestro afán es cubrir todos los diversos tipos de empresas que forman el sector, por ello, cuatro de los cinco emplazamientos pertenecen a grandes empresas, mientras que uno es una pyme.

El centro piloto francés, Fenouillet, propiedad del grupo Granulats Vicat, se encuentra en el centro de una zona comercial de Toulouse y cuenta con vecinos tan visitados por cientos de personas como un Decathlon o un McDonald's que, poco a poco, se han instalado en sus inmediaciones. Este piloto tiene la particularidad de no contar con un lugar de extracción vinculado directamente, ya que su función principal es procesar y valorizar materias primas procedentes de movimientos de tierras realizados en la zona. Los materiales que se producen al final del proceso que llevan a cabo se utilizan tanto para alimentar una planta de hormigón instalada dentro de sus instalaciones como para ser suministrados a sus clientes directos. Este piloto es muy importante ya que, en efecto, es muy raro encontrar una plataforma de reciclaje de tal envergadura en las inmedia-

El equipo de DigiEcoQuarry durante una de las visitas realizadas a las canteras piloto del programa: Valdilecha (Hanson) en las afueras de la ciudad de Madrid.

ciones de un gran centro comercial y que, además, sea capaz de producir materias primas, como lo son los áridos para la fabricación de hormigón, valorizadas y de buena calidad.

En Fenouillet se instalará y pondrá a punto un "software" de automatización para el control de la producción, así como sistemas de sensores inteligentes para la maquinaria. También se desarrollará una innovadora trituradora móvil equipada con un tren de potencia híbrido y una avanzada tecnología de captación de ruido y polvo.

El emplazamiento español que forma parte del programa es Valdilecha, situado en las proximidades de Madrid, es una cantera de piedra caliza perteneciente al grupo Hanson HeidelbergCement. Esta cantera produce alrededor de 1,2 millones de toneladas al año, que se distribuyen, fundamentalmente, a las industrias de la construcción y del carbonato cálcico. Sus actividades principales incluyen la producción y distribución de cemento y áridos.

DigiEcoQuarry pretende, gracias al trabajo realizado en este piloto, mejorar la calidad de la fragmentación de la roca y probar nuevos sistemas que contribuyan a aumentar sus estándares en materia de seguridad y salud en el trabajo y también en lo relativo al medioambiente. Con un enfoque novedoso del proceso denominado como 'desde la perforación hasta la planta de tratamiento', en Valdilecha se examinará el funcionamiento de nuevos explosivos así como una nueva perforadora que evaluará las características de la roca para diseñar la voladura con la máxima precisión. Este proceso conlleva dotar a los equipos móviles y fijos de la explotación con sensores, lo que permitirá supervisar todo el proceso y recopilar gran cantidad de información con el objetivo de recabar datos que se puedan extrapolar a otras empresas del sector.

Asimismo, se desarrollarán algoritmos de inteligencia artificial para mejorar el control de la producción: uno de

CyA

El proceso de trabajo de DigiEcoQuarry de un vistazo con cada una de las áreas, y las instituciones encargadas de su desarrollo, especificadas.

ellos permitirá, mediante colorimetría, saber la calidad de la roca entrante en el primario y el segundo, su tamaño, para detectar posibles riesgos debidos a material sobredimensionado que pueda causar daños en los elementos de trituración.

El piloto italiano, Pioltello San Bovio, por su parte, es propiedad de Holcim Aggregati Calcestruzzi, que, a su vez, es una empresa del Grupo Holcim, uno de los principales actores del cemento en el mercado del norte de Italia. Pioltello San Bovio, situada cerca de Milán, no se trata de una explotación al uso, sino que es una gravera con extracción por dragado. En esta explotación se producen 400.000 toneladas de áridos al año que se utilizan, fundamentalmente para la construcción, hormigón prefabricado y el cemento, entre otros.

Los socios que forman parte del equipo del proyecto desarrollarán en Pioltello San Bovio modelos de optimización de trituración y cribado para la mejora del rendimiento, incluido un gemelo digital de la criba, un 'doble digital' de la explotación para este proceso. Además, se llevará a cabo la automatización completa de la línea de trituración incluidas cribas, trituradoras, silos, cintas transportadoras y sistemas de pesaje, así como la línea de ciclones y el sistema de gestión del agua. A su vez, se colocarán sensores de monitorización y herramientas de análisis para controlar

el transporte interno y alimentar el sistema de gestión con datos relevantes. También se analizarán imágenes tanto satelitales como de cámaras para la comprobación del volumen de los acopios.

La cantera alemana de Mammendorf pertenece a Cronenberger Steinindustrie Franz Triches GmbH & Co. KG (CSI), una filial de Pescher Beteiligungen GmbH & Co. KG. Esta cantera está situada en la formación de roca dura más septentrional de Alemania y extrae y procesa una media de 1,2 millones de toneladas de andesita. Esta materia prima se destina a la construcción de la base de los firmes de las carreteras, al hormigón asfáltico, al balasto ferroviario, escolleras y otros usos.

Este piloto ha sido seleccionado para formar parte del proyecto con el fin de profundizar en el potencial de ahorro energético de todo el proceso y reducir el impacto ambiental, asuntos de vital importancia para el desarrollo de la minería sostenible en los que esta cantera cuenta ya con años de experiencia. Entre ellos destaca la renovación constante del parque de maquinaria; la formación especial continua de los conductores; el uso de "software" específico de cada casa para obtener y usar datos sobre el consumo de combustible y el tiempo de inactividad; el empleo de un sistema automatizado de control de la presión de los neumáticos con sensores en todas las máquinas y un sis-

tema de gestión de la flota basado en datos GPS. La planta se equipará con micrófonos y cámaras para detectar posibles averías en cintas y cribas, señalando así los riesgos de posible mal funcionamiento de la maquinaria. Gracias a su experiencia, este piloto dirigirá la prueba de eficiencia energética, la modelización en tiempo real y la recogida de datos y vallas digitales o 'geovallas'.

Por último, la cantera portuguesa Alenquer, situada cerca de Lisboa, pertenece a AGREPOR, propiedad del gran productor portugués de cemento, CIMPOR. Esta explotación produce cerca de 1,3 millones de toneladas de piedra caliza al año, gran parte de las cuales se destinan a la producción de cemento. Esta cantera será el piloto de referencia en todo lo relacionado a la optimización de almacenamiento y transporte. A su vez, se llevará a cabo una digitalización de la planta y se monitorizará mejor el flujo de material para tener más controlados los acopios. Además, se desplegarán diversos sensores y tecnologías para maquinaria móvil, tanto para la optimización del transporte interno como externo. Con esta información, se generarán modelos estadísticos y análisis sobre la producción y los costes, transmitiendo información sobre cómo podrían mejorarse los procesos para generar más ingresos.

Sumado a todo lo anterior, en los cinco emplazamientos se diseñará un modelo BIM (Building Information Modeling, una metodología colaborativa de trabajo para diseñar y gestionar de proyectos) para diagnósticos avanzados, análisis de operaciones, programación y gestión de flotas de canteras.

Conclusión

DigiEcoQuarry, para todos los que lo hemos visto nacer y trabajamos cada día en su crecimiento con la mejora de la minería y su desarrollo sostenible en mente, es una oportunidad y un desafío. Es una oportunidad para mejorar la sociedad en la que vivimos a través de nuestro trabajo que, por otra parte, es fundamental para el desarrollo sostenible europeo y es un desafío porque sabemos que, en gran medida el reto es muy ambicioso. Al fin y al cabo, casi todas las cosas que merecen la pena de verdad lo son.

Este proyecto, que pone en valor tanto la colaboración entre diversos sectores (el tecnológico, el académico, el empresarial, el minero, etc.), entre diversos países (de Portugal a Finlandia) e, incluso entre varios continentes (no olvidemos que entre los miembros del consorcio que forma DigiEcoQuarry hay un representante de Colombia y otro de Sudáfrica), aúna, proyecta y prueba que la colaboración es la vía a través de la cual se pueden buscar soluciones que mejoren nuestro día a día.

La industria europea de extracción de áridos es, con diferencia, la mayor industria extractiva no energética de la UE (Eurostat 2017). Se estima que en Europa hay unas 26.000 explotaciones extractivas, el 81,26% del total de explotaciones mineras y canteras de la UE. Además, sabemos que cada año se procesan 3.000 millones de toneladas de áridos que se suministran directamente al mercado interior de la UE, labor que emplea a alrededor 220.000 personas de manera directa.

Por otro lado, sabemos que la UE se enfrenta a la necesidad de un futuro sostenible y competitivo para las materias primas europeas, especialmente en el sector de la construcción, debido al crecimiento previsto de la demanda de productos relacionados con el desarrollo sostenible, la salud, la seguridad y la sostenibilidad.

DigiEcoQuarry explotará el gran potencial de la industria de los áridos a través de un enfoque coordinado hacia la gestión de los materiales de construcción con el objetivo final de reducir la dependencia del suministro exterior de la UE y de liderar un uso eficiente de los recursos.

Entre las herramientas que usará esta iniciativa para lograrlo está el desarrollo de sistemas, tecnologías y procesos para la digitalización integrada y la automatización del control de procesos en tiempo real. El trabajo realizado en estos pilotos permitirá mejorar la eficiencia de los procesos maximizando los recursos de las canteras, la gestión sostenible del agua y las emisiones de energía, al tiempo que se minimizan el impacto medioambiental y se amplía el negocio de los áridos y la construcción en la UE.

La conjunción de diversos enfoques entre los que se cuentan la inteligencia artificial, los sistemas 'ciberfísicos' y el concepto de 'Internet de las cosas', hace posible el planteamiento de asimilar la minería a la 'industria 4.0' y hacen realidad la posibilidad de poder contar con explotaciones sostenibles e inteligentes.

Todas las fases del proceso, desde la extracción hasta el usuario final, están cubiertas por DigiEcoQuarry, garantizando la comunicación con los responsables políticos, las actividades de aceptación social y la cooperación internacional con Colombia y Sudáfrica para compartir conocimientos y mejores prácticas. El desarrollo de un innovador Sistema Inteligente de Canteras (Intelligent Quarrying System, IQS) aumentará el suministro sostenible de minerales para el sector de la construcción, además de permitir la extracción sostenible de los recursos minerales de la UE en canteras existentes y nuevas.

En resumen, el proyecto DigiEcoQuarry no solo mejorará la eficiencia y rentabilidad de las canteras y graveras, sino que supondrá un gran avance debido a las mejoras en materia medioambiental, de seguridad y salud, y social que traerá consigo.

Design and Usage Example of a Data Warehouse in the Context of the DigiEcoQuarry Project by Sigma

Design and Usage Example of a Data Warehouse in the Context of the *DigiEcoQuarry* Project

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Abstract

It is not always obvious the role that a data warehouse plays in many projects. It often seems that it solves the same problem as an operational database. In the context of the *DigiEcoQuarry* project, it is not obvious how to implement a data warehouse and the role it plays to answer the business questions used to run a quarry. In this document, we provide an example use-case that aims to illustrate how a data warehouse fits in the project and how it is designed. As a result, we show how a simple data warehouse is designed and how to write an SQL query to answer a hypothetical business question. This document justifies why the data warehouse is needed in the *DigiEcoQuarry* project and illustrates how it is intended to be used in the context of the project.

Keywords: *DigiEcoQuarry*, *Data Warehouse*, *Data Warehouse Design Methodology*.

1. Background

The main purpose of a data warehouse is to provide answers to business questions based on data extracted from a data storage as explained in (Kimball & Ross, 2013). Data is normally extracted using SQL queries that are closely related to the business questions that need to be answered.

In contrast to a traditional database, information is stored in a way that matches the point of view of the information used to measure the business, instead of the point of view of the operations that run the business. Therefore, the data warehouse requires the information to be organized in a way that eases building queries to answer the business questions.

The design method described in (Kimball & Ross, 2013) relies on the business questions that need to be answered in order to make decisions that affect the business. In this document we focus on the following example question in order to design the data warehouse structure and to build the query that answer the question:

What is the average volume of each pile of aggregate by day in 2022's Q1?

The following sections discuss the references that support our methodology, the design of the tables of the data warehouse, and the SQL queries built to answer the questions.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/dissemination/>

Stenkoll by Chalmers

■ EU - PROJEKT

Europeisk plattform för digitaliserade tänkter

Forskningsgruppen Chalmers Rock Processing Systems och Roctim deltar i de två EU-projekten DigEcoQuarry och Rotate. Chalmers och Roctims uppgift är att bidra med teknik för beräkningar av miljöpåverkan. Flera delar av Vinnova-projektet EPD Berg, som Stenkoll berättat om tidigare, kommer att användas i arbetet.

TEXT: Niclas Kindvall

Av de båda EU-projekten är DigEcoQuarry det som kommit längst och byggandet av en digital plattform har inletts.

– Ambitionen är att skapa en plattform för hela Europa, berättar Chalmers Gauti Asbjörnsson. I plattformen samlas data in från alla processer i en täkt, allt från sprängdata till energiförbrukning och produktionssiffror.

Datan samlas in automatiskt via sensorer, behandlas med olika algoritmer och visualiseras sedan i plattformen. Resultatet kan sedan användas i optimeringssyfte, såväl för effektivare produktion som för minskad miljöpåverkan.

Fem pilottäkter från olika delar av Europa är utvalda för tester av valda delar av DigEcoQuarry.

Sedan i augusti är Chalmers och Roctim även inblandade i EU-projektet Rotate.

– I Rotate ingår det flera insatser för att öka resursutnyttjande, återvinning och utvecklingen av en miljöplattform. Plattformen består av sex moduler där vår del handlar om miljö- och processberäkningar. I detta projekt är fokus mer på hållbarhet och cirkulära flöden, och i denna plattform ingår även moduler för ener-

"Ambitionen är att skapa en plattform för hela Europa. I plattformen samlas data från alla processer i en täkt."

Gauti Asbjörnsson

gibesiktning, biologisk mångfald, dammbekämpning, optimering och efterbehandling.

Att Chalmers valts ut för att arbeta med just de här delarna visar att Sverige ligger långt framme, något som inte minst EPD Berg är ett bevis på.

– Det är roligt att se att vad vi arbetar med här hemma väcker uppmärksamhet i hela Europa, säger Gauti Asbjörnsson. Det ska bli spännande att arbeta med båda de här fyraåriga EU-projekten och att se hur övriga länder hanterar samma utmaningar när det kommer till miljö och återvinning. ♦

LÄS MER om DigEcoQuarry

12 Annex II. Events

SDMI abstract by Montanuniversität Leoben

Addressing energy efficiency in quarries – First stage in the development of a holistic approach

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Introduction

Large amounts of energy are consumed across the different unit processes of the mining value chain, e.g. loading and hauling, comminution, and milling. Accordingly, energy efficiency has long been an important concern in the industry. Energy management actions have been researched and developed transversally, initially driven by the need to reduce operational costs, but increasingly also aiming to improve the sustainability of operations. Energy consumption relates directly to greenhouse gas emissions, thus improving its efficiency or moving to cleaner energy sources is critical in a climate change context and under the scrutiny of communities and general stakeholders¹.

Among the different mining industries, quarries represent the largest portion of global mineral production², significantly impacting the environmental footprint of the entire sector. Hence, the importance of working towards more sustainable quarrying operations.

The research project in which this paper is framed aims to introduce further digitisation and automation in the quarrying sector in Europe, to enhance economic, environmental, and safety indicators, towards sustainable and ethical mining practices. Subsequently, this specific study focuses on addressing energy efficiency. As a first step, this document presents an overview of how this topic can be tackled comprehensively in quarries. For this purpose, energy consumption at a range of small to medium-scale quarries is assessed. The main energy-related challenges are analysed, considering the distinctive nature of each site, geology, processes, and products. Likewise, potential rooms for improvement for different quarry scenarios are identified.

Methodology

Five quarrying companies provide the pilot sites to test and validate the technologies and strategies developed in the project. These operations are located in five different countries of Europe, and exploit diverse products, granting a wide perspective on the quarrying sector.

The analysis of energy efficiency in the project follows two complementary approaches. First, a general assessment is conducted, considering the general layout of each site, machinery, processes, and related practices. The goal is to achieve a deeper understanding of the energy requirements of quarries, main consuming processes, and the most relevant challenges.

The second approach consists of applying data analysis techniques, e.g. statistical methods, and machine learning, to model the relationship between operational parameters and overall energy consumption. As a result, global energy efficiency strategies can be developed, and environmental performance enhanced. The data will be collected, stored, and accessed through a series of sensors, cameras, and digital platforms, implemented as part of the project's efforts to digitise and automate quarries. In this paper, the primary findings of the general assessment (first approach) are discussed.

¹ Igogo, T., Awuah-Offei, K., Newman, A., Lowder, T., & Engel-Cox, J. (2021). Integrating renewable energy into mining operations: Opportunities, challenges, and enabling approaches. *Applied Energy*, 300, 117375.

² Oberle, B., Bringezu, S., Hatfield-Dodds, S., Hellweg, S., Schandl, H., & Clement, J. (2019). *Global resources outlook: 2019*. International Resource Panel, United Nations Enviro.

General assessment

Table 1 summarises the main features of the sites, indicating the relevant energy-consuming equipment in each case. As it can be seen, quarries in this project, as in general, employ different technologies and configurations according to their specific characteristics, i.e. geology, size, location, overburden, and others. Additionally, Figure 1 shows the average annual electricity and fuel/diesel consumption at each site, along with the specific consumption per ton of material produced.

Generally, material handling and comminution are the most energy-intensive processes, but at the same time the ones with the most potential for improvement³. Correspondingly, these areas have been identified as the ones consuming most of the energy in the analysed operations.

Preliminary, fleet optimisation, i.e. the optimal amount of loaders and trucks, and reduction of idle times, have been proposed as strategies to explore in sites 1, 2, and 3. On the other hand, improvements in the operation of conveyor belts, i.e. better integration between different sections for coordinated functioning will be examined in sites 4 and 5. In parallel, analysis of other sources of energy, e.g. renewables, or switching from fuel to electric-powered equipment is also part of the study.

Final comments and next steps

This first approach allows exploration of the key leveraging points for improvement, but also to design the proper strategies for data collection and analysis in the second stage of the project. Likewise, set the basis for proposing suitable prediction and optimisation models to achieve energy efficiency goals and environmental impact reduction.

As mentioned, energy efficiency is crucial from the sustainability point of view, but also from the cost perspective. Currently, energy represents between 30% and 60% of the operational cost of the investigated sites. Moreover, if no actions are taken, this could increase in the upcoming period, as energy prices continue to rise. However, if the energy reduction goals in the project are met (5%-20%, depending on the source and site), annual savings between €600,000 and €1,000,000 can be expected (considering current energy prices).

Table 1. Description of pilot sites.

	Site #	1	2	3	4	5
General	Extraction method	Drill & blasting	Drill & blasting	Drill & blasting	Dredging	None
	Main product	Limestone	Andesite	Limestone	Sand & gravel	Recycled material
	Product[kt/y]	1,300	1,200	1,200	400	41
Machinery consuming fuel and diesel	Drills	✓	✓	✓		
	Excavator		✓	✓		
	Mobile crusher		✓	✓		
	Wheel loader	✓	✓	✓		✓
Machinery consuming electricity	Trucks	✓	✓	✓		
	Dredge				✓	
	Conv. belts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Screeners	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Crushers	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

³ Awuah-Offei, K. (2016). Energy efficiency in mining: a review with emphasis on the role of operators in loading and hauling operations. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 117, 89-97.

Figure 1. Electricity and fuel/diesel consumption of sites.

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Fragblast paper by UPM-M

Rock Fragmentation by Blasting - X. G. Wang (ed)

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Mechanically operated probe to survey ring-blastholes in a safe and efficient way

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a mechanically operated probe integrated in an explosive charge-up unit. The probe is equipped with centralisers to minimize the measuring error. The system allows to place the probe inside blastholes drilled in any direction and to survey along its length by mechanically pushing the hose, while the operator stays in a safe position and views the records in real time in a handheld PC. This configuration allows to measure the trajectory of up-holes in a safe and efficient way with minor disruption of production. The system records automatically dip and azimuth angles, providing a data set from the inwards path and another from the outwards path. These double data set enables to apply the standard deviational ellipse (SDE) concept to calculate the toe's position and its associated uncertainty. A real-time quality indicator based on the miss-out (or distance between the Cartesian coordinates of the toe from each path) is developed to ensure a limited uncertainty at the toe's position. Measurements in two sites demonstrate the suitability of the system to detect drilling deviations that may compromise blasting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Drilling accuracy is evaluated in terms of borehole deviation or distance between the designed path and the real one at hole's toe or bottom. Deviation is often normalized by the borehole's length (Stiehr and Dean, 2011) and is a key factor in blasting performance. Error in collar positioning, deviations from the initial orientation of the rig's boom, and rod bending modify the blasthole path from the intended (Östberg, 2013; Singh, 1998), thus leading to an uneven explosive energy distribution within the rock mass. This has a major influence in explosive performance, ore recovery, fragmentation, haulage and processing costs, and over/under excavation of the remaining rock mass and therefore in rock stability problems and ore dilution (Amjad, 1996; Heberle et al., 2017; Jones, 2019; Mohanty and Zwaan, 2015; Oppong and Agyei, 2020; Scoble, 1994; Sellers et al., 2013).

An accurate knowledge of the hole paths is a

valuable information for decision making. It allows to drill extra boreholes when deviations are large, and to vary the explosive's density along the borehole, to get higher energies in areas with an excessive distance between holes or, on the contrary, lower energies where the charge concentration is large. It is also helpful to mitigate the sources for such deviations, like calibration errors of the orientation sensors in the boom, poor rig navigation, or excessive thrust on the rock (Amjad, 1996).

Normally, only the blasthole's collar is accessible from the ground surface, while the rest of the hole till the other end is inside the rock mass and its position cannot be obtained with land surveying systems, such as total stations. The fact that blastholes are not straight also prevents to survey and locate their toe position from the surface.

Under these conditions a probe equipped with sensors to record its attitude (i.e. orientation of the probe in the 3D space defined by dip and

azimuth angles) along the borehole is usually used. From the recorded data and the collar coordinates, the Cartesian XYZ coordinates of successive points along the blasthole can be obtained using desurveying methods. This allows to estimate the 3D trajectory of the hole and to estimate the hole's deviation with respect the designed path, with the exception of the collaring error position that ought to be measured by other means and it is not covered in this study.

The specific conditions of underground mining with small hole's diameters, rough walls crossed by discontinuities, and production costs limitations restrict the design of the surveying system and, ultimately, its accuracy. The main characteristics of a representative sample of blasthole surveying systems used nowadays in drill and blast monitoring is shown in Tab. 1. Most of the instruments have a data storage system and power supply as well as the sensors inside of the probe to record data automatically and then transferred it wirelessly once the probe comes out of the hole after finishing a survey.

The current trend is to measure dip and azimuth angles with Inertial Measurement Units, IMUs. This is the case of four of the systems in Table 1 that are typed in italics, while the other two use inclinometers to measure the dip and magnetometers or dual set of inclinometers to record the azimuth. IMUs are composed by accelerometers and gyroscopes oriented in three orthogonal directions. North-seeking or relative gyroscopes are valid to measure the azimuth in metallic mines as they do not have magnetic interferences from the ore deposit and metallic elements used in underground rock support. North-seeking gyros provide a reading of the absolute angle against the geographic North. They are significantly larger and more expensive than relative gyros, which obtain their turning angle from a predefined starting direction by integrating the angular velocity over time (Jamieson, 2012). This integration causes the accumulation of error, which is, among other reasons, due to the gyro drift that is proportional to the measured time

and represents the major error source. This ranges from 0.0001°/h for strategic grade sensors to 1°/h for the tactical grade sensors, which are significantly cheaper, around 2000 EUR (El-Sheimy and Youssef, 2020).

Commercial systems in Tab. 1 have consistent errors that are in general around 1° for azimuth, and about 0.3° for dip; only the first system has errors one order of magnitude smaller.

Tab.1 Characteristics of representative borehole survey systems used in drilling and blasting

Systems	Handling mode	Recording	Accuracy
<i>Devigyro^a</i>	Manual with a push reel system	Automatic	A: ±0.1° D: ±0.1°
<i>Borettrak^b</i>	Manual with cable	Manual	A: ±1.0° D: ±0.2°
<i>Borettrak^c</i>	Manual with rods	Manual	A: NA D: ±0.2°
<i>Borettrak^d</i>	Manual with cable or rods	Manual	A: NA D: ±0.1°
<i>M-Sense^e</i>	Manual with cable	Manual	A: ±1.0° D: ±0.5°
<i>S Sense^f</i>	Automatic integrated in surface drilling rig	Automatic	A: ±1.0° D: ±0.5°

^aDevico (2019); ^bCarlson (2019); ^cCarlson (2019); ^dCarlson (2021); ^e Robit (2021a); ^f Robit (2021b).

The existing instruments are manually operated except for cable reels for down-holes (which do not pose any difficulty) and Robit's S-sense system (Robit, 2021b) which is integrated in an open pit drilling rig, thus allowing an immediate survey after drilling each hole. Surveying of blastholes is common in open pit blasting, where the direction of the holes (downwards) allows to drop the probe (any of the manual probes in Tab. 1) along the hole with the help of a cable reel and then brought back upwards by hand. Surveying of horizontal boreholes (typically of 4-5 m) in development headings and up-holes (10-35 m) in up-holes rings is more complicated. A boom lifter is required to reach the blasthole collar (exception are the holes located in the low part of the face drift that can be directly surveyed from the ground), as well as a set of rods to push the probe manually along the hole. These

working conditions represents a notable risk, especially in longer production boreholes typical of sub-level open stope.

As far as the authors are aware, there is a lack of a system specifically designed to measure up-holes in a safe and efficient way with minor disruption of production. This leads to a lack of knowledge regarding the real borehole trajectories in underground mines, thus creating a gap between the drilling and blasting stages.

To overcome this issue, a probe has been integrated in an explosive charging unit (Laguillo et al. 2022). The unit's crane and hose pusher are used to move the probe to the borehole collar and push/pull it along the borehole, while the operator starts and stop the measurements from a safe area, and views the records in real time in a handheld PC.

The system records automatically the probe's attitude from the collar to the toe in the inward and from the toe to the collar in the outwards path. These datasets allow to report the toe's position together with a quantitative statement of its uncertainty (or dispersion in the reported magnitude). This information, usually unknown in hole-deviation surveys performed in mining, is very helpful in a post analysis stage but also in the field at the moment that the measurement is made. This will allow the operators to be more efficient when measuring by both being

sure that the surveyed samples are correct and that if there are large errors, they can repeat the survey without having to go down in the mine for a second time.

This paper summarizes a previous work by the authors (Laguillo et al., 2022). It describes the characteristics of the system, the operating procedure, the instrument field performance and the definition of a quality criterion to accept surveys on real time.

2 SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The main components of the surveying system are shown in Fig. 1; they are:

- A probe equipped with two centralisers, CRs (see Fig. 2), and equipped with IMUs (i.e. triaxial gyroscopes, triaxial accelerometers and processing filters) to measure dip and azimuth angles;
- A cabled charging hose to move the probe along the hole, to supply electrical power, and to enable data transfer;
- An encoder that measures the probe's position (i.e. depth inside of the borehole);
- A data retrieving, logging, and displaying system installed in a handheld PC (see Fig.2);
- The connection systems between the different elements.

Fig. 1 Borehole surveying system

Fig. 2 Detail of the probe and handheld PC

The hole diameter assessment was a goal in the early stages of the project, but the need of getting a robust instrument and the absence of casing or tubing in the hole's walls prevents to incorporate this measurement into the mechanically operated probe.

2.1 Probe design

Specifications of the probe, including the output of IMUs sensors can be found in Tab. 2. They allow measurements in upwards and downwards boreholes drilled in any direction in magnetic susceptible environments, metallic ore deposits and nearby metal supporting elements.

Cost may be a limiting factor for many operations, and as North-seeking gyroscopes were unaffordable, tactical grade relative Micro-Electro-Mechanical System (MEMS) gyroscopes have been used. This type of sensors is selected as a compromise solution between their cost and gyro drift. A Kalman filter is implemented to reduce the sensors' errors (El-Sheimy and Youssef, 2020; Guo and Hong, 2019; Jamieson, 2012). The accuracy in the dip is in line with the systems shown in Tab. 1, but as the azimuth measuring accuracy depends mainly on the gyroscope's drift, it is necessary to carry out field tests to assess the resulting error. This should be small enough to detect deviations from the intended design that could compromise blast's performance.

Tab. 2 Probe, sensors and outputs characteristics

Probe		
Dimensions	Length = 900 mm; Diameter = 50 mm; Weight = 4.5 kg	
Protection grade	IP68 (ANSI 2004)	
IMU outputs	Accelerometer	Gyroscope
Range	±8 g	300 °/s
Bias instability	±0.04 mg	8 °/hr
Processed outputs		
Azimuth and dip range	360° & ± 90° in each direction.	
Sensors' resolution	< 0.01°	
Sensors' repeatability	0.2°	
Dip accuracy with Kalman filter	± 0.25° RMS associated with a confidence level of 68.3%	

In up-holes the force of gravity makes the probe to fall on one side, which causes the probe to be misaligned with the hole's axis. The resulting misalignment error associated to the probe dimensions is in the range of other commercial probes, i.e. about 4 cm/m (Laguillo et al., 2022). This causes inaccuracies significantly higher than the sensor's accuracy, having a direct impact in the instrument's overall performance. To make this error negligible, the centralizing system around the probe shown in Fig. 2 has been specifically designed for measurements in up-holes. Further discussion on the effect of the centralisers in the quality of field measurements is made in Section 5.

2.2 Description of the rest of the system

The probe is fixed at the tip of a cabled hose which supplies electrical power from the charging unit to the probe and which transfers data in real time while performing the measurements between the probe and the handheld PC. Usually, in commercial probes, data is retrieved from the probe wirelessly once this comes out of the hole after each survey, which does not allow for a rapid decision on survey quality as opposed to the real-time readings, that are possible with the cabled hose by which the probe is continuously transmitting data. The characteristics of the cabled hose overcome at the same time the possible obstacles associated with rough walls, cracks, irregularities

ties, and dislocations along the hole that sometimes prevent reaching the toe. The system performs continuous readings of dip, azimuth, and depth that are recorded automatically and displayed into the handheld PC at a sampling frequency of 4 Hz (i.e. up to 24 samples/m for the recommended hose speed range). This feature prevents stopping at successive depths to perform each reading, as occurs with many other existing systems.

3 MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE

The working area must be first assessed, especially to ensure correct rock conditions and to keep a safe distance from the crane's radius of operation. Before surveying, all blastholes are checked first with an auxiliary hose that is replaced by a cabled hose in which the probe is mounted. Next, the probe is set up and aligned with an external reference direction. For this, a laser system mounted on the probe is utilized, so that it can be aligned to the surveying marks that are placed in the drift, either on the walls or on the roof, to position the drilling rig. It is advisable to repeat this procedure after measuring

various holes in order to check the readings' consistency and to reduce the possible errors related to gyro drift.

Once the preparatory steps are completed, the operator uses the explosive charging unit's crane and hose pusher to elevate the probe from the ground towards the hole collar, to place it inside the hole, and to displace it along the latter at a constant velocity in the range of 6-10 m/min. In a less competent rock mass, the speed needs to be lowered as the blockage risk is much higher than in a competent rock mass.

The suggested operating procedure to survey a borehole is described in Fig. 3; solid rows represent probe motion, while discontinuous rows describe quality measurements.

After collaring the probe, the surveying stages consist in moving it along the hole, inwards from the collar to the toe and outwards back to the collar (indicated with blue and orange boxes, respectively, in Fig. 3), while the instrument is recording automatically azimuth, dip, and depth.

Fig. 3 Operating procedure

During the survey, the probe is stopped at five points for few seconds as a real time check of the stability of the azimuth reading (refer to the green box in the center of Fig. 3). This ensures that the gyroscope's drift does not produce a systematic increase of the azimuth as the survey progresses which would involve large errors in the toe's position.

Once the survey is finished, the uncertainty at the bottom of the hole is assessed (refer to the green box at the bottom of Fig. 3). The aim is to detect in real time measurements with large errors (refer to Section 5.1 for further details), and allow the operator to repeat the survey, avoiding the need of going down in the mine on a later shift to repeat incorrect measurements. The entire process takes about 8-10 min for a 20-25 m long hole.

4 DATA PROCESSING

For each survey, a double data set of dip and azimuth angles is obtained as function of depth; one is obtained in the inwards path and another in the outwards path. Despite the centralizing system, the probe moves within the blasthole due to uneven wall conditions, causing inherent fluctuations in the dip and azimuth records. To filter them out, Central Moving Averages (CMA) are applied onto the dip and azimuth readings. The average interval width considered depends on the existing noise and it is taken between one and two times the probe length, i.e. 0.90 m.

To calculate Cartesian coordinates of the 3D hole trajectory from surveyed data (i.e. dip and azimuth), desurveying two-point methods are considered. They use data from adjacent points to compute the next incremental horizontal and vertical positions from the known previous station point (Yang et al., 2019). Examples of these methods (sorted from lower to higher complexity) are: tangential, balanced tangential, average angle, radius of curvature, and minimum curvature. Several works (Codling, 2019; Eren and Suicmez, 2020; Škrjanc and Vulić, 2016) state that the impact of any of these methods on the resulting paths of exploration boreholes would be very little when the spacing between measuring stations is suffi-

ciently small with respect to the survey tool length as it is the case of our measurements (i.e. about 2.78 %). The application of these methods on the data measured by the probe has been investigated, involving, in line with existing works, negligible differences in the toe's position and a marginal variation in the resulting accuracy and uncertainty.

The ease of implementation (Škrjanc and Vulić, 2016) is the principal factor considered to decide the use of the average method. This method provides the hole coordinates at the j^{th} station point as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X_j \\ Y_j \\ Z_j \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} X_0 \\ Y_0 \\ Z_0 \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^j \begin{pmatrix} \Delta X_i \\ \Delta Y_i \\ \Delta Z_i \end{pmatrix} \text{ for } j=1, 2, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

where (X_0, Y_0, Z_0) are the collar coordinates, N is the number of measurements of either the inwards or outwards paths, and $\Delta X_i, \Delta Y_i$ and ΔZ_i are calculated as follows:

$$\Delta X_i = \Delta L_i \cos\left(\frac{I_i + I_{i+1}}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{A_i + A_{i+1}}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta Y_i = \Delta L_i \cos\left(\frac{I_i + I_{i+1}}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{A_i + A_{i+1}}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Z_i = \Delta L_i \sin\left(\frac{I_i + I_{i+1}}{2}\right) \quad (4)$$

and I_i and A_i are the dip and azimuth angles at the i^{th} data points of either the inwards or outwards paths, respectively and ΔL_i is the distance between consecutive data points.

5 SYSTEM IN-FIELD PERFORMANCE

Eleven boreholes were surveyed at two mining sites identified as A and B. Mine site A is representative of sub-level open stope mines, while Mine site B is an open pit limestone quarry. A summary of the measurement characteristics is shown in Tab. 3. Every blasthole was surveyed two or three times with the probe to assess the repeatability of the measurements under the testing conditions.

At Mine site A, the standard measuring procedure described in Fig. 3 is followed. Some

holes were surveyed without centralisers at Mine site B, where the explosive-charging unit was not used, thus the probe was adapted to be operated manually with a hose (push and pull by hand) and an auxiliary encoder to measure the depths during the survey. Common align-

ment practice, followed in quarry blasting, for other probes with relative azimuth measurement was also followed. This consists in aligning the probe with the direction defined by the row of holes and assuming that they were drilled perpendicularly to this direction.

Tab. 3 Characteristics of the field tests

Site	Drill rig	d_h^a , mm	l_{hs}^b , m	Type	Measuring procedure	No. holes (No. surveys)
A	Epiroc simba M6	102	16.0-17.5	Sub-vertical cross-through holes	Standard according to Fig. 3	2 (3-5) with CRs ^c
B	Atlas copco smartroc T45	89	16.8 - 19.5	Sub-vertical	The probe is aligned according to the hole's intended direction and it is handled manually.	4 (2-3) with CRs ^c 5 (2-3) without CRs ^c

^a d_h , hole diameter; ^b l_{hs} , hole length surveyed; ^cCRs, centralisers.

Measurements in site A are used to quantify errors (i.e. accuracy and uncertainty) at the toe's position under suggested measuring conditions, while the effect of other measuring conditions, mainly manual handling of the probe and use of centralisers, is investigated from surveys in site B.

5.1 Survey quality acceptance criteria

In order to illustrate the variability between measurements in the inwards and outwards paths,

processed records from the same survey in two holes (B02 and B22) at site B are shown in Fig. 4. Dispersion in dip angles is limited for both holes, while variability in the azimuth described as the median of the standard errors along the hole is small in hole B02 (0.54°, left bottom graph) and large in B22 (2.72°, right bottom graph). Such differences are mainly caused by the gyroscope's drift which occurs even though it is limited and controlled by the use of the Kalman filter together with the stabilization points.

Fig. 4 Measured angles for blastholes B02 (left) and B22 (right)

Application of the average angle desurveying method to the inward and outward datasets leads to different paths and also to different toe's position as it is depicted in Fig. 5, where

the blue marker is the hole bottom coordinates from inward measurements and the orange one for the outwards. The miss-out or distance between them normalized by the hole's length is

employed to assess the overall survey quality. It is low (0.13 cm/m) in hole B02 (left graph), while it is high (2.6 cm/m) in B22 (right graph).

Fig. 5 also shows the toe position for 5 000 simulated sets of azimuths and dips (grey dots). These are obtained sampling the normal distribution of the mean of the angles (azimuth and dip) at each depth, i.e. normal distribution with mean equal to the average of the angles from both paths (A_i and D_i) at the i^{th} point and with standard deviation equal to the standard error of the mean (δA_i and δD_i) obtained from circular statistics (Berens, 2022) at that point.

The most probable toe's coordinates for each

survey are within the bounds defined by the Standard Deviational Ellipse, SDE (Gong, 2002; Lefever, 1926; Yuill, 1971) that is calculated from the simulated toe positions using a Matlab function (Johnson 2015). The resulting SDE at a 95% confidence level for surveys of holes B02 and B22 is shown in Figure 5 (left and right graphs, respectively). The centre of the SDE is the estimated toe's position (black marker); the minor axis defines the direction of minimum dispersion; and the major axis is the direction of largest variability in the data. The latter is taken, from a conservative point, as a measurement of the uncertainty in the toe's position (Domínguez Garcia-Tejero, 2007). It is 0.087 m for hole B02 of 18.6 m and 0.33 m for hole B22 of 16.9 m.

Fig. 5 Toe's position and associated uncertainty for blastholes B02 (left graph) and B22 (right graph) (all coordinates have been normalized by subtracting the mean position)

To define a threshold miss-out, the uncertainty at the toe's position for all available data is plotted versus the corresponding miss-out in Fig. 6; data is differentiated as function of the site and the use of centralisers. Three data clusters from high to low uncertainty are apparent.

- The first cluster is representative of measurements with high uncertainty, near 2 m (or 11 cm/m), and high miss-out. It includes one measurement, associated to a poor performance of the instrument.
- The second cluster lumps measurements with uncertainties in the range 0.28-0.78 m (or 1.7 - 4.0 cm/m) and miss-outs generally above 2 cm/m. They are obtained in sur-

veys in site B in which no centralisers were mounted on the probe.

- The third cluster corresponds to limited uncertainties, below 0.21 m (1.31 cm/m), and miss-outs, below 2 cm/m. It encompasses most measurements with centralisers (94%) in site A and few of the surveys made without them in site B(28%).

Uncertainties of the last group of measurements could be deemed acceptable, considering the usually difficult conditions of underground production drilling that result in drilling errors that often amount to several tens of centimeters (Jones, 2019; Minnovare, 2022). Examples of such deviation (mean and standard deviation following "sd.") are 11.0 sd.

3.0 cm/m (Orive et al. 2017) and 10.0 sd. 3.5 cm/m (Navarro et al., 2019). Consequently, a miss-out of 2 cm/m that separates measurements with medium and small uncertainties (see green and blue markers, Fig. 6), can prove to be very useful to decide whether a survey made according to the operating procedure in Fig. 3 should be repeated before moving on to the next blasthole.

Fig. 6 Uncertainty at toe's position versus miss-out (The ordinate axis has been broken to show the survey with high-uncertainty)

5.2 Repeatability

Repeatability in the toe's coordinates between surveys of the same hole is calculated from the major axis of the SDE of the simulated positions obtained from the dip and azimuths angles recorded in each survey; the confidence level is 95%. Results from the five surveys of hole A1 are plotted, as an example, in Fig. 7 (top graph); a different color is used to differentiate data from each survey. In this case, the clouds from the different surveys clearly overlap and dispersion is limited (i.e. high repeatability), being the resulting uncertainty between surveys 0.99 cm/m.

Repeatability in the toe's position from the other hole surveyed in site A is also excellent, and about half the maximum uncertainty assigned to good quality surveys (i.e. 1.31 cm/m). The statistics of the resulting uncertainties at each site are summarized in Tab. 4; data has been normalized by the borehole length and the mean and standard deviation of the miss-out is given in brackets as a reference of the

quality of each survey.

In Mine site B, four of the surveys made without centralisers lead to miss-outs above the acceptance limit (i.e., 2 cm/m) and they have been discarded. This reduces the number of available holes with repeated surveys from nine to five. Repeatability is worse, with an average error that is twice such in mine site A. Uncertainty between surveys is above 2 cm/m in two holes surveyed with centralisers and in one surveyed without them.

Despite that the quality of the surveys in site B is good (the mean miss-out is limited, 0.6 cm/m), the manual handling of the probe (see Tab. 3) produces an unsteady movement along the hole with higher displacement velocities, about 13 m/s, than the recommended ones, and thus larger variability between surveys, mainly in the azimuth angles. This may involve, statistically significant differences in the toe's position between surveys (i.e. the points clouds do not overlap), as occurs in three holes surveyed in site B. Fig. 7 (bottom graph) shows the results for hole B11 with the largest uncertainty between surveys.

5.3 Accuracy

The two cross-through boreholes drilled in site A, identified as A1 and A2, connected two access drifts separated 19 m vertically. This sort of rarely performed drilling allows to get the position of both the collar and toe of the hole using a total station. The accuracy of the instrument used, a Leica Nova MS50 multistation, is 1 mm + 1.5 ppm onto prism in distance and 1" in the horizontal and vertical angles. No prism was used when pointing towards the collar and toe of hole A1. This deters using these data to assess the system accuracy, as no limited errors are obtained from the total station compared to the hole surveying system. This issue was corrected for hole A2, that was also surveyed three times with the hole deviation probe following the procedure in Fig. 3 (see Tab. 3). This results in a limited variability at the toe position between surveys of 0.62 cm/m (see lower bound of uncertainty for measurements in site A in Tab. 4).

Fig. 7 Toe's position repeatability between surveys of borehole A1 (top) and B11 (bottom) (all coordinates have been normalized by subtracting the mean position)

Tab. 4 Repeatability in the toe's coordinates between surveys of the same hole

	Site A	Site B
No. of holes	2 with CRs ^a	4 with CRs ^a 1 without CRs ^a
Uncertainty		
Mean/cm·m ⁻¹	0.80 (0.82)	1.57 (0.59)
Standard dev/cm·m ⁻¹	0.26 (0.57)	0.71 (0.52)
Range/cm·m ⁻¹	0.62 - 0.99	0.52 - 2.31

^aCRs, centralisers.

The accuracy in the toe's position is calculated as the distance between the coordinates obtained with the total station (the borehole is treated as a straight line between the collar and end coordinates) and the blasthole surveying

system (the procedure described in Section 5.1 to simulate the hole paths is applied to each of the three available surveys).

The mean and standard deviation of the resulting errors at the toe level are 0.21 sd. 0.034 m (or 1.17 sd. 0.19 cm/m). These errors are smaller than the uncertainty between surveys and, in average terms, are equal to two times the borehole diameter (see Tab. 3). This figure is in good agreement with the objective of the system of detecting typical borehole deviations found in underground mining. More measurements would be required, however, to increase the statistical significance of this result.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work makes a thorough description of a borehole surveying system specifically developed to assess the blastholes path in underground mines. The probe equipped with IMUs sensors and centralisers is handled, as a novelty, with the hose, crane and hose-pusher system of an explosive charge-up unit for underground operations, which allows the operator to place the probe inside a borehole drilled in any direction and then to survey it along its length by mechanically pushing the hose. The pushing system allows to overcome possible obstacles associated with rough walls, cracks, irregularities, and dislocations along the hole that sometimes prevent reaching the toe. The system enables the personnel to have a risk-minimized operation as there is no need for manual handling and work at heights from a boom lifter to reach the borehole collar as it has to be done currently with existing equipment in the market in ring-production up-holes.

For each survey, a double data set of dip and azimuth angles is obtained as function of depth for the inwards and outwards paths; the system resolution depends on the hose speed, and the former is about 30 mm for the recommended velocities. The data is recorded and displayed in real time on a handheld PC in contrast to existing systems that provides these data once the probe comes out of the hole.

The Cartesian coordinates of the inwards and outwards paths are obtained applying the av-

erage desurveying method after filtering the noise in the raw datasets. The toe's position and the associated uncertainty are assessed from the 95 % confidence standard deviational ellipse (SDE) calculated from the recorded angles.

The system provides in real time the miss-out (or distance between the Cartesian coordinates of the toe from the inwards and outwards surveys of the same hole). This parameter is a good descriptor of the uncertainty in the toe's position. Miss-outs smaller than 2 cm/m guarantee good quality surveys with limited uncertainties (i.e. below 1.3 cm/m) in the toe's position when the standard configuration of the probe with centralisers is used. Higher miss-outs involve larger uncertainties suggesting wrong measurements due to the misalignment of the probe with the borehole axis and/or due to an excessive gyroscope's drift, which is more probable when the suggested operating procedure is not followed.

Results from field tests provides a repeatability between surveys and an accuracy in the toe's position in the range of 1 cm/m when the recommended operating procedure, which basically includes setting the reference direction of the gyroscope, mounting centralisers, and handling the probe mechanically, is followed. These results outline the suitability of the system to detect drilling deviations, often of amount to several tens of centimetres that compromise blast results.

Future work will be to include the hole surveying system in a wide number of underground mines to investigate procedures for correcting uneven energy distribution within the rock mass due to hole deviations from the intended design. This will allow, at the same time, to enlarge the dataset, specially the number of cross-through holes, and to increase the statistical significance of the in-field system performance (i.e. accuracy and repeatability between measurements).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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SMI by Chalmers

Thursday, 10 november

Venue: Wood hotel, Safe conference room, Skellefteå

- 08:00 Morning files and registration
- 08:30 Short Introduction/Welcome
- 09:00 Hållbara (1/2)
- 09:40 The need for raw materials to drive the green transition
- 10:00 Initial Report, Geological Survey of Sweden
- 10:30 Remote teaching - how industry and academia can build stronger collaboration
- 11:00 Martin Karlsson, Northvolt
- 11:15 PhD research across the mining value chain - session 1
- 12:00 SMI PhD student network members
- 12:00 Lunch (Shared bowl)
- 13:00 PhD research across the mining value chain - session 2
- 14:00 SMI PhD student network members
- 14:00 All in mining
- 14:30 David Lagerstedt, Boliden
- 14:30 Afternoon file
- 15:00 PhD research across the mining value chain - session 3
- 15:00 SMI PhD student network members
- 15:30 Arctic Sweden - the most impactful region of the world. About it's promises and challenges
- 16:00 Henrik Gustafsson, IMST
- 16:00 Modellers - Technology and investments enabling the smart, green industrial transformation
- 16:30 Daniel Gustav, Skellefteå
- 16:30 Dinner (Shared bowl)

Friday, 11 november

- 08:00 Departure by bus from Best Western Malmis, Visit to Northvolt Ett
- 09:00 Visit to Boliden Rönnskär smelter
- 12:00 Lunch at Kopparmojjen
- 13:00 Sustainability RnD
- 13:45 Erik Burman, Boliden
- 13:45 Mineral Exploration and opportunities in Europe and beyond!
- 14:30 Sören Johansson, Boliden
- 14:30 How to kill you colleagues and get away with it
- Peter Burman, Boliden

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- Broad industrial experience

Work Smarter Not Harder:

Integrating Environmental Management into Operational Improvements in the Aggregates Industry

DIGIECOQUARRY aims to design, develop, and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated digitalized, automatic, and real time process control for aggregates quarries. This will be translated into:

- Health & Safety and Security**
Upgraded H&S and Security conditions for workers, avoiding their exposure to dangerous operations through automated and controlled processes.
- Efficiency, Selectivity and Profitability**
Enhanced selectivity and Efficiency of the aggregate sites, thus increasing the profitability of the process, ensuring long-term operational sustainability and viability.
- Environmental Impact**
Maximizing sustainability and ensure Efficiency **reducing emissions** improving the management of water and ensuring a sustainable supply of Raw Materials.
- Social Acceptance**
Improved social acceptance through the communication with policy makers, citizens and relevant actors to get them involved in the value chain.

Companies and organizations

13Annex III. Partners' dissemination track record

Table 4. ANEFA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ANEFA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		4
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		4
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Anefa actualidad. Jan - Feb - Mar 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa-actulidad_64	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Apr – May – Jun 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_65	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Jul - Aug – Sep 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa66	D9.3
H2020 de la Comisión Europea aprueba financiar el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY ideado y liderado por ANEFA	https://www.aridos.org/h2020-de-la-comision-europea-aprueba-financiar-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry-ideado-y-liderado-por-anefa/	D9.3
Arranca el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.aridos.org/arranca-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
El “international Advisory Board” del Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.aridos.org/el-international-advisory-board-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Oct - Nov – Dec 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefaactualidad67	9.4
Anefa actualidad. Jan - Feb – Mar 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_68_v2	9.4

Anefa actualidad. Apr - May – Jun 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_actualidad_69	9.4
Anefa Online 179	https://www.aridos.org/novedades-en-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	9.4
Anefa Online 180	https://www.aridos.org/reunion-del-comite-tecnico-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	9.4
Anefa Online 181	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-empieza-a-tomar-forma-la-plataforma-para-la-gestion-inteligente-de-la-cantera/	9.4
Anefa Online 182	https://www.aridos.org/primer-hito-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry-superado/	9.4
Anefa Online 183	https://www.aridos.org/olimpiadas-y-sprints-finales/	9.4
Anefa Online 184	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-continua-su-trabajo-de-campo/	9.4
ANEFA Online 185	https://www.aridos.org/proyectos-europeos-firma-de-un-grant-agreement-inteligencia-artificial-broche-de-oro-y-un-premio/	9.6
ANEFA Online 188	https://www.aridos.org/cuenta-atras-para-milan/	9.6
ANEFA Online 189	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-celebra-su-reunion-anual-en-milan/	9.6
ANEFA Online 190	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-cierra-el-ano/	9.6
ANEFA Online 191	https://www.aridos.org/la-primer-version-de-los-data-lake-del-proyecto-deq-inicia-sus-pruebas-en-los-5-pilotos/	9.6
ANEFA Online 192	https://www.aridos.org/deq-en-valdilecha-nuevo-video/	9.6
ANEFA Online 193	https://www.aridos.org/anefa-en-el-evento-minero-mas-importante-del-mundo-liderando-deq-rotate/ https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-aprueba-con-nota-la-primer-revision-tecnica-de-la-comision-europea/	9.6
Anefa actualidad. Jul – Aug – Sep 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_70_ok	9.6
Anefa actualidad. Nov – Dec 2022 – Jan 2023 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_72_web_ab6a66ed2be600	9.6

Anefa actualidad. Feb – Mar 2023 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_73_web	9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		4
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
SMOPYC, International Show of Public Works, Construction and Mining Machinery	November 2021, Spain	D9.3
European Minerals Days	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Jornadas de otoño - Emprendimiento e innovación hacia la sostenibilidad	September 2022, Spain	D9.6
BIMExpo	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
Seminar for Advancement of the Aggregate Industry	November 2022, Korea	D9.6
AFA Extremadura and Castilla La Mancha meetings	February 2023, Spain	D9.6
PDAC	March 2023, Canada	D9.6
Webinar: AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries	March 2023, Spain-USA	D9.6
Hannover Messe	April 2023, Germany	D9.6
Energy efficiency workshop	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
ANEFA's general assembly	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Interview to César Luaces Frades (PC) in Aggregates Business Europe		D9.3
Radio interview		D9.6

Table 5. GRANULATS VICAT's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: GRANULATS VICAT		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 6. HANSON's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: HANSON		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 7. HOLCIM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: HOLCIM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Lanciato Digiecoquarry: il Progetto chiave per la digitalizzazione del settore degli Aggregati	https://concretenews.it/2021/06/11/lanciato-digiecoquarry-il-progetto-chiave-per-la-digitalizzazione-del-settore-degli-aggregati/	D9.3
	https://www.edizionipei.it/notizie/news/lanciato-digiecoquarry-il-progetto-chiave-per-la-digitalizzazione-del-settore-degli-aggregati.htm	D9.3
	https://www.gowem.it/DigiEcoQuarry-Holcim	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
ANEPLA assembly	November 2022, Italy	D9.6
Workshop Holcim	March 2023, Italy	D9.6
Workshop at SaMoTer w/ Ma-Estro	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 8. CSI's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CSI		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Andesit „Gestein des Jahres 2020/21	September 2021	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 9. CIMPOR's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CIMPOR		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 10. SANDIVIK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: SANDIVK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 11. METSO OUTOTEC's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: METSO OUTOTEC		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 12. MAXAM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MAXAM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
A novel borehole surveying system for underground mining: Design and performance assessment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224122002895	D9.4
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
MAXAM announces its participation in the DIGIECOQUARRY project	https://www.maxamcorp.com/en/newsinsights/news/maxamannouncesparticipationdigiecoquarry	D9.3
Maxam is focusing on customer solutions	https://www.quarrymagazine.com/2022/11/14/maxam-is-focusing-on-customer-solutions/	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Energy efficiency workshop	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 13. ITK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ITK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
MIRO Forum	November 2021, Germany	D9.3
BAUMA 22	October 2022, Germany	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 14. MONTANUNIVERSITÄT LEOBEN'S dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MONTANUNIVERSITÄT LEOBEN		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Digitalisation for a more sustainable mining industry	https://www.unileoben.ac.at/en/newsdetail/durc-h-digitalisierung-zu-einem-nachhaltigerem-bergbau/	D9.3
Stein und Kies	Paper	D9.4
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry - SDIMI 2022	September 2022, South Africa	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 15. CHALMER's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CHALMERS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Stenkoll	paper	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
SMBI Production I	November 2022, Sweden	D9.6
IMPC Asia-Pacific 2022	August 2022, Australia	D9.6
Swedish Mining Innovation PhD Student network workshop	November 2022, Sweden	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 16. UPM-M's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: UPM-M		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
A novel borehole surveying system for underground mining: Design and performance assessment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224122002895	D9.4
On the Influence of Sampling Scale on the In Situ Block Size Distribution	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-02953-1	D9.6
A Non-parametric Discrete Fracture Network	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-03194-y	D9.6
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
Fragblast 13	October 2022, China	D9.6
ISEE	February 2022, USA	D9.6
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 17. UPM-AI's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: UPM-AI		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Geochemical characterization of geological lacustrine formations in Central Spain	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260714_Geochemical_characterization_of_geological_lacustrine_formations_in_Central_Spain	D9.6
La digitalización de minerales y rocas para la enseñanza virtual de Geología	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260141_Digitalizacion_de_minerales_y_rocas_para_la_ensenanza_virtual_de_la_Geologia	D9.6
La enseñanza virtual de geología y minería a través de MOOCS	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260294_LA_ENSEANZA_VIRTUAL_DE_GEOLOGIA_Y_MINERIA_A_TRAVES_DE_MOOCS	D9.6
Modelos geológicos 3D y digitalización de afloramientos	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260405_MODELOS_GEOLOGICOS_3D_Y_DIGITALIZACION_DE_AFLORAMIENTOS	D9.6
Acercando los autocodificadores variacionales al gran público	https://documentacion.sea-acustica.es/publicaciones/Elche22/ID-55.pdf	9.6
Radiofrequency absorbance as a novel concentration indicator in sucrose aqueous solutions	https://revistas.unal.edu.co/index.php/ingenv/article/view/94695	9.6
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
XIII Iberian Geochemical Congress	April 2022, Spain	D9.4
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
X USATIC International Congress	June 2022, Spain	D9.6
FECIES	September 2022, Spain	9.6
TECNIACÚSTICA 2022 (53ª International conference of acoustic technologies)	November 2022, Spain	9.6
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable

4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System"	December 2021	D9.4
Spanish Geology Olympics	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Expominerals	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Field trips of the School of Mines and Energy of Madrid	April 2022, Spain	D9.4
Spanish Science Week	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
Spanish Science Week	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 18. AKKODIS's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: AKKODIS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 19. ARCO's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ARCO		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		2
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Participación Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.arcoelectronica.es/noticias/participacion-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 20. MAESTRO's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MAESTRO		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		2
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
SaMoTer	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
Workshop at SaMoTer w/ Holcim Italy	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 21. DH&P's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: DH&P		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
MIRO Forum 21	November. Berlin, Germany	D9.4
MIRO Forum 22	November. Berlin, Germany	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 22. ABAUT's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ABAUT		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 23. APP's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: APP		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
BIMExpo	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 24. SIGMA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: SIGMA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Sigma cognition	https://sigmacognition.ai/digiecoquarry/	D9.4
Design and Usage Example of a Data Warehouse in the Context of the DigiEcoQuarry Project by	paper	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Webinar: AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries	March 2023, Spain-USA	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 25. DGASTUR's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: DGASTUR		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Arranca el Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.fae.es/arranca-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 26. ASOGRAVAS's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ASOGRAVAS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	3	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
Sexto Encuentro Nacional de la Industria de Agregados	September 2022, Colombia	D9.6
MaPric	November 2022, Chile	D9.6
Expomin 2023	April 2023, Chile	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 27. MINTEK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MINTEK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
Joint Research Centre (JRC) Training Webinar	October 2021	D9.4
South African Institute of Quarrying Conference	March 2022, South Africa	D.4
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 28. ROCTIM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ROCTIM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 29. ZABALA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ZABALA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		0
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable